

D3.2 – Enhanced upcycled high temperature TES materials

WP 3, T 3.2

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Executive summary

This document is the deliverable “D3.2 / Enhanced upcycled high temperature TES materials” of the eLITHE project (project reference: 101138325). The main body of this deliverable is characterized by the results of the analysis of the material cyclic stability of eLITHE-provided waste materials as well as recommendations for material enhancement techniques.

The main goal of T3.2 – Material cyclic stability and performance enhancement as TES media, is to evaluate the long-term stability of the waste materials as potential TES materials by investigating their performance under cyclic conditions, including intraday and slow storage behaviour. These analyses are meant to serve as a basis (in conjunction with results from T2.6) for making final material recommendations that would be proposed for deployment in commercialized TES systems.

Within this document, the considered materials as received by project’s partners, are first listed and described including different ceramic wastes and ashes. Slags from different metallic production processes are also included as comparative materials, often considered for thermal energy storage applications. Secondly, the performed tests are described with their key parameters. To maximize the interpretation and usability of the results, key measurement points were defined and labelled along the test, serving as a key for referencing experimentation points throughout the text. Next, the main results describing the material structural and weight stability during and after the tests are summarized. The presented results served as a basis for providing final material recommendations. These recommendations were finally highlighted in conjunction with identified material enhancement suggestions/techniques.

The obtained data highlights the potential of waste ceramic material, especially clinker wastes, to be exploited, as received, for thermal energy storage applications. Further characterization will be performed in the context of WP3 and the potential storage design to be integrated within the ceramic industries and production lines to maximize flexibility will be performed in T3.3.

The delivery of this deliverable is done in accordance with the description in the Grant Agreement Annex 1 Part A with no time deviation and no content deviation from the original planning.

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NOMENCLATURE

Table 1: Acronym List

Acronym	Definition
TES	Thermal Energy Storage
MP	Measurement Points
Eq.	Equation
TPS	Transient plane source
RH	Relative humidity
TGA	Thermogravimetric analysis
MS	Molten salts
HTF	Heat Transfer Fluid

Table 2: Symbols List

Symbol	Definition
Δm	Relative weight change
M	Mass

Table 3: Subscripts List

Subscript	Definition
L	Long-period thermal stability test Measurement point designation
C	Thermal cycling test Measurement point designation
ref	Reference value
f	Dust separation measurement point designator
i	i-th measuring point
d	Dust separation relative weight change designator

1 Introduction

eLITHE aims to **decarbonise the ceramic industry** by demonstrating cost-effective and sustainable solutions for the electrification of high-temperature thermal processes. To achieve this goal, the project is slated to implement innovative technologies such as **microwave-based furnaces, hybrid tunnel kilns, and advanced smelters**, and test them at three pilot sites. The project also aims to explore control and flexibility tools for the electrified processes and consequently encompasses continued analysis and refinement of Thermal Energy Storage (TES) Systems. As part of this TES improvement initiative, T3.2 builds on the high-temperature circular TES material database developed in T2.6 to investigate material cyclic stability and performance enhancement of the TES materials.

The main goal of T3.2 is to further characterize the circular TES materials under long term and cyclic operation to identify potential material treatment techniques that could maximize their characteristics and suitability for use in high temperature TES operation. This investigation will provide a basis for identifying and proposing final materials suitable for deployment in commercialized TES systems (TRL 7).

The deliverable is organized in four main sections. The first section contains a brief description of the TES materials considered. These materials were received from the project partners and have been earlier characterized in T2.6. The second section highlights the methodology executed to test the materials under both long duration and cyclic thermal conditions. The third section contains the results, observations, and analysis obtained from the performed tests and the final section discusses probable material enhancement based on literature survey and some test findings.

1.1 Considered TES materials

The TES materials tested include 3 waste ceramics received from IZF, 2 ashes from Torrecid and 3 metallic slags that are used for benchmarking as shown in Table 4. The 3 ceramics are clinker, roof tiles and hollow bricks which were all received, from IZF, as fragmented pieces in similar sizes within a 10 to 100 mm range. The ashes were received, from Torrecid, in powder form (wet and dry) which would most likely require further treatment or additives to be used in packed bed TES applications. The dry ash was obtained from filter recovery in Torrecid's frit furnace, while the wet ash consisted of a soft wet mixture of solid waste from the water treatment plant combined with frits and raw materials from the process' solid press. Table 5 presents the typical material composition of the waste materials. These composition values are merely representative and may vary depending on the raw material feed and process parameters amidst other factors.

Table 4: TES materials summary

<p>Clinker (IZF)</p>		
<p>Dry ash (Torrecid)</p>		
<p>Reference materials for benchmarking</p>		
<p>Brass slags</p>		

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Table 5: TES material composition by mass in %

Clinker (% Comp)	CaO	SiO ₂	Al ₂ O ₃	Fe ₂ O ₃	MgO	K ₂ O	SO ₃					
	60-67	17-25	3-8	0.5-6	1-3	< 1	< 3					
Roof Tiles (% Comp)	SiO ₂	Al ₂ O ₃	Fe ₂ O ₃	Others (CaO, MgO, K ₂ O, etc.)								
	50-60	< 20	< 10	< 5								
Hollow Bricks (% Comp)	SiO ₂	Al ₂ O ₃	Fe ₂ O ₃	CaO	MgO	Others (Na ₂ O, K ₂ O, organic matter, etc.)						
	50-60	20-30	5-10	1-5	1-3	1-3						
Wet Ashes (% Comp)	SiO ₂	Al ₂ O ₃	CaO	ZrO ₂	ZnO	Na ₂ O	K ₂ O	MgO	P ₂ O ₅	SrO	Fe ₂ O ₃	SO ₃
	59.712	18.898	5.483	5.246	2.932	2.67	1.95	1.03	0.31	0.296	0.252	0.12
Dry Ashes (% Comp)	B ₂ O ₃	K ₂ O	ZnO	Na ₂ O	Cl	SiO ₂	CaO	Cl	SO ₃	Al ₂ O ₃	MgO	FeO
	48.23	17.69	12.42	7.20	4,15	3.28	1.61	1,81	1.36	0.58	0.5	0.05
Brass slags (% Comp)	Cu	Zn	Cr	Others (As, Al, Sb, Ba, Be B, Cd, Co, Hg, Mo, Ni, Pb, Se, Sn, Tl, Th, Te, Ti, V, etc.)								
	50.59	38.53	0.016	10.864								
Copper slags (% Comp)	Cu	Zn	Cr	Others (As, Al, Sb, Ba, B, Cd, Co, Hg, Mo, Ni, Pb, Se, Sn,Th, etc.)								
	61.407	0.0194	0.0105	38.57								
Steel slags (% Comp)	CaO	Fe ₂ O ₃ & FeO	SiO ₂	MgO	MnO	Al ₂ O ₃	P ₂ O ₅	Fe	S			
	40-60	10-40	10-19	5-10	5-8	1-3	0.5-1	1-10	<0.1			

The long duration and cyclic tests were conducted for all 8 materials, with steel, copper and brass slags being analysed as benchmarking materials due to their widespread consideration in TES applications.

2 Material testing methodology

This section summarizes the methodology undertaken to conduct the long duration and cyclic thermal tests on the potential TES materials previously highlighted. Figure 1 provides a visual overview of the temperature trends and Measurement Points (MPs) throughout the testing process with a detailed description given in Table 6. These MPs are cited throughout the section to improve clarity and ease of reference. The positioning of the TGA (Thermogravimetric analysis) labels in Figure 1 indicate that the test was done in T2.6 before the commencement of the present task. The results of the TGA testing are used in this work as initial benchmarking.

A long exposure test for a total of more than 300 hours, divided into 3 stages, have been performed to assess the influence of long exposure at high temperatures (800°C) under air environment.

A cyclic test for a total of 30 thermal cycles between 400 and 800°C has been performed to evaluate the influence and material stability ones subjected not only to high temperatures but also to thermal cycles and the consequent thermal stresses associated with rapid heating and cooling.

Figure 1: Temperature trends and measurement points for long duration and thermal cycling tests

Table 6: Description of Measurement points (MPs)

Long-exposure Thermal Stability		Thermal Cycling		Thermogravimetric Analysis (TGA) – from T2.6	
MP	Description	MP	Description	MP	Description
L0	Initial sample before long duration testing	C0	Initial sample before thermal cyclic testing	TGA0	Initial sample before TGA Test
L1	After 100 hours at 800 °C	C1	After 10 thermal cycles between 400 °C and 800 °C	TGA1	TGA measurement point at 800 °C
L2	After 200 hours at 800 °C	C2	After 20 thermal cycles between 400 °C and 800 °C	TGAf	After ramp down post-TGA1 (1 Cycle)
L3	After 300 hours at 800 °C	C3	After 30 thermal cycles between 400 °C and 800 °C		
Lf	After dust separation from material post L3	Cf	After dust separation from material post-C3		

2.1 Long Exposure Thermal Test Description.

The long-duration thermal cyclic test involved the exposure of the TES material samples to an air-based environment at temperatures up to 800 °C for three consecutive 100-hour intervals using a high-temperature furnace (Thermconcept® HTL 04/16) as shown Figure 2. Prior to testing, the materials were carefully sized and placed in separate ceramic (alumina) crucibles before being inserted into the furnace as shown in Figure 3.

Figure 2 (a) High temperature Thermconcept furnace used for material tests (b) Material samples in ceramic crucibles placed inside the furnace for thermal testing

Figure 3: Photographs of TES material samples before long duration test commencement (L0)

The test duration was selected based on previous studies indicating that TES material degradation usually occurred after the first 100 hours [1]. The full long-duration test was conducted without replacing the samples, and visual inspections along with weight measurements were performed at the start and at 100-hour intervals (MPs L0, L1, L2, and L3) throughout the test. Ramp rates of 3.2°C/min and 1.8°C/min were used as heating and cooling rates respectively during the test duration.

2.2 Thermal Cycling Test Description.

After the long duration test, the samples were renewed (being prepared in similar manner as in the long duration test) to properly assess the influence of thermal cycling. The thermal cycling test was conducted by performing three blocks of 10 consecutive thermal cycles between 400°C and 800°C. The minimum and maximum temperature limits were selected to align with typical packed-bed TES applications and previous TES material tests [1]. Heating and cooling rates were both set at 3 °C/min, with dwell periods of 15 min and 20 min at peak and valley temperatures respectively. The heating and cooling rates, as well and dwell times have been selected based on the expected typical transient operations faced by high temperature TES units in industrial contexts and considering the limitations of the furnace. Visual inspections and weight measurements were also assessed at the beginning and at the end of each cycle (MPs C0, C1, C2, and C3).

2.3 Material performance assessment

The influence of both long-duration and thermal cycling tests on TES materials was evaluated using qualitative and quantitative methods. Qualitative measurements involved visual inspections of material changes at each MP and quantitative measurements involved

the tracking of weight changes along each MP. The material weight changes were analyzed in relative terms using Eq. (1) below upon the completion of each test.

$$\Delta m = \frac{M_{MP} - M_{MPref}}{M_{MPref}} \quad (1)$$

Where:

M_{MP} = material mass at the MP of interest, and

M_{MPref} = reference MP used for comparison (L0 and C0)

Eq. (1) served the reference for mass comparison and was utilized as the base for various comparisons of interest. For example, the weight changes of TES material samples during long-duration and thermal cycling tests are calculated using modified forms of Eq. (1), as shown in Eq. (2a) and (2b), respectively.

$$\Delta m_L = \frac{M_{L,i} - M_{L0}}{M_{L0}} \quad (2a)$$

$$\Delta m_C = \frac{M_{C,i} - M_{C0}}{M_{C0}} \quad (2b)$$

Material disintegration and dust formation was also characterized for both tests by comparing the material weight after its separation from disintegrated and dusty material with its initial pre-test weight as shown in Eq. (3a) and (3b), respectively.

$$\Delta m_{d,L} = \frac{M_{L,f} - M_{L0}}{M_{L0}} \quad (3a)$$

$$\Delta m_{d,C} = \frac{M_{C,f} - M_{C0}}{M_{C0}} \quad (3b)$$

Where:

$M_{L,f}$ = dust separated material mass (post-L3)

$M_{C,f}$ = dust separated material mass (post-C3)

Finally, the weight changes observed in the tests were compared with Thermogravimetric Analysis (TGA) results from T2.6 for contrast. The TGA earlier performed involved the in-situ measurement of TES material sample weight-loss trends with temperature variation.

3 Results and Discussion

This section summarizes the outcomes of testing activities and provides explanations and discussions of the mechanisms causing the weight changes, material changes and degradation. The section also elaborates on opportunities for material upgrading.

3.1 Long exposure thermal stability test results

Results from long-residence thermal stability tests showed that all materials retained visible structural integrity under prolonged high-temperature exposure, except dry ash. The dry ash showed significant volume loss, adhered closely to the crucible after the first run at L1, and cracked the crucible during the second run at L2 as captured in Figure 4. The dry ash sample was excluded from subsequent tests to mitigate the risk of molten liquid migration from the dry ash crucible to other crucibles, since the remaining tests were conducted at higher temperatures. The behaviour of the dry ash sample during testing can be attributed to its material composition (see Table 5), which consists largely of non-metallic oxides (primarily B_2O_3). These oxides are less stable than metallic oxides at high temperatures and tend to react with other materials, potentially releasing gases. Further investigation at lower temperatures is recommended to determine the threshold for its suitability, as the material has been shown to be unstable under the high-temperature conditions associated with the eLITHE project.

Figure 4: Photographs of Dry Ash Material Transformation during the first two long duration tests (L0, L1 & L2)

The wet ash samples exhibited significant, though positive, changes – transitioning from a marshy, pasty state to a hardened solid structure comparable to other metallic slag materials. Although the compressive strength and thermomechanical properties of these transformed wet ash samples have not yet been quantified, they seem to visibly possess strong potential for use as TES materials. The hardening of these wet ash samples is likely attributable to their composition (see Table 5), which consists primarily of metallic oxides – whose sintering tends to get consolidated at high temperatures. Further details on the behaviour and potential applications of wet ash samples will be provided in the following subsections.

The ceramic materials exhibited no visible changes throughout the long-duration tests, as shown in Figure 5. In contrast, some of the metallic slags displayed slight discoloration due to oxidation, with brass turning yellow and copper developing a reddish-like hue.

Figure 5: Photographs of TES material samples at Measurement Points L1, L2 and L3 during Long residency test

Significant weight changes were also recorded for some of the TES material samples during the long duration thermal tests as captured in **Error! Reference source not found..** Wet ash experienced the most significant weight change losing about 20 – 25% of its initial weight. This weight reduction could likely be attributed to the evaporation of water content and the release of gases during smelting of non-metallic and metallic oxides at high temperatures – a behaviour linked to the frit-like nature of wet ash [2]. The metallic oxides exhibited oxidation-related weight gains (0.5% - 5%) during the test which turned negative for the steel slag (-3.5%) after dust separation, reflecting the steel slag's tendency to produce some dust particles under thermal variations. The ceramic materials also exhibited slight weight variations during testing. Amongst them, hollow brick showed the greatest change with a weight reduction of about 2%, followed by roof tiles with an approximate 0.7% gain. Clinker displayed the smallest change, gaining roughly 0.25% in weight. The ceramic samples remained relatively stable with respect to material disintegration, as weight changes after dust removal were negligible.

The weight reduction data from the long-duration test was also compared with Thermogravimetric Analysis (TGA) results from T2.6, as shown in **Error! Reference source not found..** The TGA results differed significantly from those of the long-duration test,

recording mass losses for all materials except brass slags. This is in contrast to the long-duration tests which showed mass gains for all materials except hollow brick. A plausible explanation is that the TGA samples, being very small with a high surface area, likely retained more moisture. Thus, its subsequent drying probably caused more pronounced weight changes compared to the cycling test. Therefore, the results from the long-duration test are considered to most closely reflect the mass loss expected during normal operation.

Figure 6: Weight changes between TES material samples' weight at L0 and at MPs L1, L2, L3 and Lf respectively during the long residency thermal test

3.2 Thermal cycling stability results

The thermal cyclic stability tests showed that all TES material samples maintained structural integrity, exhibiting behaviour similar to that observed in long-duration thermal tests. The wet ash sample solidified after the first 10 cycles and remained solid and stable throughout the test. Metallic slags displayed minor oxidation-related colouration changes, much less pronounced than seen in the long-duration tests (see Figure 7). Ceramic slags showed no visible structural changes; however, they experienced slight material disintegration weight loss compared to the long-duration tests where they (except for hollow brick) had slight weight gains even after the dust removal process.

Figure 8 captures the overall weight change trends for all materials in the thermal cycling test. The wet ash sample showed a 27.5% weight reduction, while metallic oxides exhibited oxidation-related weight gains of 1.5 – 3% during the test with the steel slags shifting to a weight change of -1.4% after the dust particle removal process.

Figure 7: Photographs of TES material samples at Measurement Points C1, C2 and C3 during thermal cycling test

The ceramic materials samples exhibited the smallest weight changes among all materials, except for hollow bricks, which showed weight reductions of up to 3%. Unlike in the long-duration tests, the ceramic materials experienced weight loss rather than gains as both roof tiles and clinker recorded weight reductions of approximately 0.2%, even after dust removal.

Comparisons between the weight change results from thermal cycling tests and the TGA measurements in T2.6 showed alignment in the direction of weight change, as all materials except brass slag exhibited weight loss. However, significant discrepancies in weight change magnitude were observed, likely because the small TGA material samples retained more moisture, making their drying more pronounced than in the cycling test as in the case of the long duration test.

Figure 8: Weight changes between TES material samples' weight at C0 and at MPs C1, C2, C3 and Cf respectively during the thermal cycling test

3.3 Recommendations for Material Selection, Treatment and Enhancement

3.3.1 Recommendation for Material Selection.

The final recommendation for the best-performing TES material is based on results from both this task and T2.6. Clinker emerges as the most promising TES material option as it has the highest density and thermal conductivity among the ceramic materials, possessing the highest structural and weight stability during the long-duration and cyclic thermal tests. The clinker samples also remained relatively unaffected during the molten salt compatibility tests executed in T2.6, making it suitable for use in both air and molten salt Heat Transfer Fluid (HTF) loops. The roof tiles come in second place, following the clinker closely in all round suitability.

The hollow bricks, despite possessing the highest specific heat capacity, seems to be the lowest performing TES material in these analyses due to its incompatibility with molten salts as well as its relatively noticeable material weight loss as compared to other ceramics. The wet ash, on the other hand, shows great potential as a TES material, being primarily

composed of silica and alumina [3][4], and hardening after prolonged exposure to high temperatures. Nonetheless, further testing is required to confirm its suitability and evaluate its performance, possibly after applying the material treatment methods outlined in the next subsection.

3.3.2 Recommendation for material treatment and enhancement

A plausible approach to enhancing the ceramic TES materials is the introduction of additives to enhance their thermal conductivity. However, this method is likely not cost-effective, as it would require crushing, remixing, remoulding, and refiring the ceramic waste – negating its economic advantage. Therefore, enhancement techniques are primarily recommended for wet ash, which lacks a defined solidified form and has not undergone any prior treatment in its raw state.

The wet ash in its slurry-like state could be extruded into brick-shaped structures of various sizes and shapes, and afterwards preheated and sintered at high temperatures through prolonged and cyclic exposure to temperatures reaching 800 °C. This prolonged and cyclic heat treatment consolidates the sintering mechanism of its silico-aluminous components, enhancing material compactness, strength, and overall mechanical properties [3].

Following these treatments, the thermophysical properties of the bricks should be tested to identify strengths and weaknesses of the solidified wet ash for further improvement. One potential material enhancement method is the addition of alumina (Al_2O_3) to the wet ash before heat treatment to improve its thermal conductivity [4]. Additional binders may also be incorporated to augment the material's mechanical properties if required.

4 Conclusions

This deliverable presents a comprehensive analysis of long-duration and cyclic thermal tests conducted on various eLITHE-provided waste and reference materials to evaluate their suitability as potential upcycled TES materials, as an extension of the work from T2.6. Material samples were prepared in ceramic crucibles and subjected to long-duration thermal tests at 800 °C and cyclic tests between 400 °C and 800 °C in a high-temperature furnace. Observations were focused on structural and weight stability to give final recommendations (in conjunction with results from T2.6) on the best material to integrate into future TES setups and identify suitable material enhancement techniques for improved material performance.

The results identify clinker as the most promising TES material. Combining high structural and weight stability during long-duration and cyclic thermal tests with the highest density and thermal conductivity among the ceramic materials tested in T2.6, clinker also shows stability in the molten salt compatibility tests, making it suitable for use in both air and molten salt Heat Transfer Fluid (HTF) loops. The roof tiles come in second place, following the clinker closely in all round suitability. Wet ash also demonstrates strong potential as a TES material, being primarily composed of silica and alumina and hardening after prolonged exposure to high temperatures. However, further testing is required to confirm its suitability and assess its performance.

The material enhancement strategies established focused primarily on wet ash, given its untreated state and lack of defined structure. The proposed technique involved the extrusion of the wet ash into brick-like forms followed by preheating and sintering under prolonged and cyclic exposure to temperatures up to 800 °C. This proposed enhancement procedure is majorly aimed at improving compactness and mechanical strength of the wet ash through consolidation of silico-aluminous components. Further improvements to the material may involve the incorporation of alumina (Al_2O_3) to enhance thermal conductivity as well as the addition of suitable binders to augment mechanical properties where necessary.

This work serves as a compendium of final recommendations for upcycled TES materials in the eLITHE project, based on thermal treatments performed alongside earlier tests in T2.6. Overall, the work aims to provide a basis for decision-making on the final materials that will be proposed for deployment in commercialized TES systems (TRL 7).

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